

Adjective word group and its types

Negmatova Marjona Islom qizi

Student of Jizzakh branch of
National university, 203-20 group

Supervisor: Teshaboyeva N.Z

Annotation

This article focuses on how post-nominative adjectives are changing in meaning as contemporary English undergoes change. Adjectives in English can function as a predicate. Adjectives have a predicative function, and their semantics are distinguished by internal qualitative diversity.

Keywords: postnominative adjectives, prenominal adjectives, transformation, preposition, postposition, adjective, predicative.

Аннотация

В этой статье основное внимание уделяется тому, как постноминативные прилагательные меняются по значению по мере того, как современный английский язык претерпевает изменения. Прилагательные в английском языке могут выполнять функцию сказуемого.

Ключевые слова: постноминативные прилагательные, преноминативные прилагательные, трансформация, предлог, послелог, прилагательное, предикатив.

Adjectives can be used to characterize an object or person's attributes on their own or in relation to another object. Adjectives modify or describe nouns and pronouns. They can be attributive (occurring before the noun) or predicative (occurring after the noun). Predicative adjectives typically follow a linking verb (such as forms of the verb "to be") that connects the subject of the sentence to the adjective. When using post-nominative Adjectives with a predicative function in a sentence, it is taken into account that they express a denotative sign. It is known that the processes of denotation and reference are not characteristic of predicative adjectives. Classical predicates combine two things: 1) a direct sign; 2) evaluation. Hence, the peculiarities of their development in denotative and qualitative structures shows that the range of meanings of predicative adjectives is expanded, they easily enter into various connotative connections, form various semantic areas . So it becomes clear that they can bring clarity to the problem of the meaning of syntactic structural adjectives, to the question of determining their type. But there is a feature that casts doubt on this opinion. There are often conflicting statements about the problem of the relationship between syntax and semantics. There is a connection between syntax and semantics. Therefore, it is

necessary to study the semantic functions of the level structures in the semantic classification. By building a re-formation system to re-translate grammatically correct sentences into grammatically correct sentences, one can discover how post-nominative adjectives behave during the transformation process and change their meaning. Postnominative adjectives as a subject of research. The group of central adjectives with a predicative function includes adjectives that can be converted into an attributive construction and maintain the same semantics. I think my attitude is more selfish – more selfish attitude But not only that, the circumstances are unusual – the unusual circumstances. I didn't have long so wait -the results came very soon and were very disagreeable - the disagreeable results The examples given describe predicative adjectives in the attributive sense without any change in the meaning of the pairs. At first glance, it seems that in both cases the same word, the same concept, and the same relation are used. In the predicate and in the transform in the cases of the idea is absurd – the absurd idea; the results were very disagreeable - the disagreeable results- nouns idea, circumstances, results are characterized as abstract expressions, agreement is highlighted. These researchers noted a special connection between the adjective and the noun, calling it an attributive-predicative connection. In English, there are compounds that express a special connection between the subject and the sign. In such constructions, the sign is, as it were, separated from the object, and as a result, the dependence between them is weakened. This approach, in our opinion, is applicable to the predicative position. A sad experience! Poor fellow is obtained at the syntactic level obtained by converting a compound like a fellow is poor. At the semantic level, such a transformation is unacceptable, and this indicates a semantic barrier. Representatives of generative grammar tried to present adjectives and attributive functions as transformations of each other, assuming that they are close to each other. In this case, the predicative construction was taken as the initial form. The attribute construction is derived from the initial form at an intermediate stage. This approach has been criticized by representatives of generative grammar. In addition to functional differences in facial development in terms of predicative and attributive function, the researchers also showed that the **N+A+N** transformation is impossible in some cases. This phenomenon is usually based on the special semantics of the adjective, which does not allow nominal transformation, as well as on the syntactic conditionality that occurs when a predicative adjective is expanded by a verb or noun group. Adjectives are associated with predicative units, and they retain certain shades of predicative meaning. Representatives of grammar also paid attention to this question .

In conclusion, semantic considerations govern the functional features of derivative words as well as the feasibility of developing an adjective in the predicative and attributive positions. The categorical affiliation of means, the semantics of combined forms, and the relationships that emerge between the elements of the corrective unit are all taken into consideration when describing the semantics of derivative adjectives. Finding the general word-forming meaning of corrective adjectives is the first step in the semantic description of these words. Certain patterns can be found in the relationship between an adjective's semantic-syntactic functionality and how complex its word formation is. As previously stated, the quality, sign, and relation of attributive words are their denotations. Qualitative words in this instance are relation, quality, and sign. This instance, attributive words also express their meaning as a quality, property, sign or relation.

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